

Quantitative assessment of landslide impacts using satellite imagery: A case study of Phuoc Son district, Quang Nam province, Vietnam

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Abstract—Landslides are considered an annual threat to mountainous areas in Vietnam during the rainy season. They can cause terrible consequences for people and infrastructure due to their sudden occurrence. This reality requires a more comprehensive approach to disaster risk assessment. It is necessary to assess the likelihood of occurrence and quantify the impact and destruction scale of such events. Therefore, this study created the impact map of a serious landslide event in late October 2020 in Phuoc Son district, Quang Nam province, Vietnam, by combining high-resolution satellite imagery data from Sentinel-2 and PlanetScope. Quantifying the impact of this landslide event was conducted by overlaying the landslide inventory map with data on houses, roads, and land use in the area. The quantitative damage data in this study achieved an accuracy of 82.2% based on verification with the damage statistical report of Phuoc Son district (local authorities) at that time. These results can provide crucial information for local authorities and communities to prepare and proactively minimize damage caused by landslides.

I. INTRODUCTION

Vietnam is one of the most disaster-prone Asian countries in the world [1]. With its geographical location in the Southeast Asian monsoon belt and diverse terrain, Vietnam is exposed to various types of natural disasters, like storms, tropical depressions,

landslides, flash floods, floods, droughts, saltwater intrusion, and forest fires. Over 70% of Vietnam's population is at risk from natural hazards, especially the rural and urban poor [2]. Flash floods and landslides occur in most mountainous and midland provinces. They are increasing in frequency, resulting in significant losses of human lives, infrastructure, and property. From 1953 to 2006, Vietnam experienced 448 flash flood and landslide events (7 events per year), and from 2000 to 2015, there were 250 flash flood and landslide events (15–16 events per year) (<http://dulieu.phongchongthientai.vn>). Economic losses due to natural hazards in Vietnam are approximately 1% of the country's GDP annually. In 2020 alone, the total damage caused by natural hazards was \$1.45 billion, nearly half the value of Vietnam's rice exports that year [2].

At the end of October 2020, the impact of Storm No. 9 caused a devastating swarm of landslides in the mountainous Phuoc Son district of Quang Nam province. Landslides with thousands of cubic meters of rock and soil buried many houses and destroyed key roads to Phuoc Kim, Phuoc Cong, Phuoc Thanh, and Phuoc Loc communes. This event claimed 13 lives. All mountainous roads in Phuoc Son district were affected, and relief work was extremely challenging. Road blockage threatened people in isolated areas to face severe food shortages [3]. This landslide event in Phuoc Son district demonstrates that disaster management

A semi-automated object-based approach for landslide detection is a process of processing and classifying areas with similar characteristics in satellite images based on spectral indices or surface characteristics. First, Sentinel-2 satellite images are collected and preprocessed, including cloud removal and light balance. Then, the threshold value segmentation algorithms are applied to divide the image into groups based on spectral and spatial characteristics. After segmentation, a polygon layer containing classified areas with different characteristics is obtained based on Sentinel-2 satellite images. Then, this data is manually compared with PlanetScope images to identify landslide areas more accurately (Figure 2).

B. Validation of landslide area determination

To check the identified areas for landslides, this study used high-resolution image data available on Google Earth Pro since it has high-quality and time-based images. According to that, the landslide areas obtained from satellite image segmentation were converted into a KML file and then uploaded to Google Earth Pro software using visual inspection of Google Earth. Furthermore, this result was also verified by local authorities and communities.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Landslide mapping

The landslide-segmented region map of Phuoc Son district was obtained by Sentinel-2 satellite images on the GEE platform and validated with PlanetScope satellite images. The segmentation results on the landslide map show about 2,300 landslide locations (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Landslide inventory map in Phuoc Son district in 2020.

The landslide locations are concentrated in 4 communes: Phuoc Loc, Phuoc Thanh, Phuoc Kim, and Phuoc Cong. These communes are mainly distributed in the southern part of Phuoc Son district and are located in the mountainous area of the district. In addition, these communes are also distributed on strongly weathered, loose soil and rock with poor cohesion and located on granite. When encountering heavy rains that last for many days, the cover layer becomes saturated and causes landslide formations.

B. Landslide impact assessment

For the housing data, the results indicated that housing damage was concentrated mainly in three communes: Phuoc Kim, Phuoc Loc, and Phuoc Thanh. In total, 110 houses were destroyed. Most of these structures were residential houses, while some may have been temporary field camps (Figure 4).

For the road network, 23.018 km of commune roads, 0.03 km of Highway 14, and 0.25 km of Highway 14E were affected by the landslide event in October 2020.

Figure 4. Damaged by the 2020 landslide events (before and after the event).

For the land-use aspect, a total of 2,943.77 hectares were impacted, including 54.72 hectares (2%) of homesteads and built-

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 up areas, 2,783.34 hectares of forest and vegetation (95%), 93.35 hectares of agricultural land (3%), and 12.36 hectares of water bodies.

C. Verification of landslide impact assessment

This study used the damage statistical report of Phuoc Son district after the landslide event at the end of October 2020 to verify the results of the landslide impact assessment. The verification results indicated that the assessment results of a landslide event in this study have an accuracy of about 82.2% (Table II).

TABLE II. LANDSLIDE DAMAGE ASSESSMENT COMPARISON RESULTS

Damage content	Damage detected from the research approach	Damage report from local authorities
Dead people (person)	-	13
Injured people (person)	-	3
Destroyed houses	110	97
Affected houses	-	69
Affected homestead and build-up areas (ha)	54.72	-
Affected forest and vegetation areas (ha)	2783.34	2300
Affected agricultural areas (ha)	93.35	120
Economic loss (billion VND)	-	750

These differences can come from various reasons: (1) Inaccurate mapping of the areas affected by the landslide/flash floods on satellite images and assumption of destruction of any elements in the affected zone; (2) The dataset used for buildings and land cover may not be fully accurate and not represent all the buildings/road/land cover at the time of event; (3) The assessed areas affected by the commune is based on rough estimate from the field, with potential underestimation, especially for remote forested areas.

V. CONCLUSION

Assessing the impact of landslides on infrastructure allows for a deep understanding of the extent of damage as well as a basis for proposing effective prevention solutions. Therefore, this study reconstructed the current landslide inventory map in late October 2020 in Phuoc Son district, Quang Nam, Vietnam, by combining high-resolution satellite imagery from Sentinel-2 and PlanetScope satellite imagery data. This landslide inventory map was overlaid with housing data, road networks, and land use to assess the impact of this landslide event on infrastructure. The results showed that housing damage was concentrated mainly in Phuoc Kim, Phuoc Loc, and Phuoc Thanh. These findings enrich the approach for

assessing the impact of natural hazards, especially for mountainous areas. Although the optical satellite imagery data used in this study have demonstrated their inherent potential in disaster management, they still have certain limitations, especially in areas with dense vegetation or cloudy weather, which may affect the accuracy of landslide data.

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